

The Birth, Life & Decline of Urdu

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Abstract

Urdu, a language born out of cultural confluence, represents a vibrant history deeply intertwined with South Asia's sociopolitical and cultural evolution. This paper explores its journey from inception to decline, focusing on its golden age, colonial influences, and current struggles, offering insights into the sociopolitical and cultural dimensions that have shaped its trajectory.

Part 1: The Birth, Life & Decline of Urdu

1 Introduction

Urdu, a language born out of the confluence of cultures, stands as a testament to centuries of South Asia's vibrant history. Emerging as a linguistic blend, it encapsulates the socio-political and cultural tapestry of a region that thrived on diversity. Historically, Urdu has transcended its linguistic function to become a carrier of tradition, art, and identity. This paper traces the journey of Urdu, from its genesis and golden age to the modern era of decline, examining the multifaceted factors that have influenced its trajectory. Central to this narrative are the socio-political changes brought by colonialism, Partition, and the pressures of modernization, all of which have shaped Urdu's legacy and survival.

2 The Birth of Urdu: Fusion of Cultures

The genesis of Urdu dates back to the 11th century, when the Middle Eastern invaders introduced Arabic, Farsi, and Turkish to the Indian subcontinent. These languages blended with local dialects, such as Brij Bhasha, Awadhi, and Gujarati, to form what was then known as Hindvi or Dehlvi. Delhi, as the administrative and cultural hub of the time, became the crucible for this linguistic synthesis.

Amir Khusrao, a 13th-century polymath and poet, played a pivotal role in championing this fusion. His famous ghazal "*Zihal-e-miskin*" masterfully combined Farsi and Hindvi, exemplifying the linguistic innovation that characterized early Urdu. This fusion, known as Rekhta, became the foundation for modern Urdu. Rekhta's adaptability and poetic potential established its place in royal courts, where it gained favor as a language of both administration and art.

The need for a common tongue for trade and governance further propelled the adoption of Urdu. Written in the Arabic script for formal purposes and the Devanagari script for local use, the language evolved to cater to diverse communities. Over time, Urdu emerged as a linguistic bridge, uniting people across religious and cultural divides, and laying the groundwork for its eventual prominence.

3 Urdu's Golden Age: The Language of Prestige

Between the 11th and 18th centuries, Urdu flourished as a language of refinement and intellect. During the Mughal era, it became the lingua franca of the elite, a medium for diplomacy, poetry, and literature. Poets such as Mir Taqi Mir, Mirza Ghalib, Sheikh Ibrahim Zauq, Bahadur Shah Zafar, Sir Allama Iqbal, Momin Khan Momin, Amir Meenai and Daagh Dehlvi immortalized Urdu through their works, which captured the depth of human emotion and philosophical inquiry.

Urdu's poetic richness made it synonymous with sophistication, as court poets were revered akin to modern-day civil servants like IAS and IPS Officers. Urdu also permeated the arts, influencing drama, music, and education. Theaters adopted it as the preferred medium for reaching audiences, while schools incorporated it into their curricula. As the administrative language of the Mughal Empire, Urdu served as a vital tool for governance, bridging communication gaps between rulers and subjects. This era cemented Urdu's status as a cultural and intellectual powerhouse.

4 700 Years of Urdu

Urdu's legacy extends over seven centuries, during which it adapted and thrived in diverse settings. It was not only the language of rulers and poets but also of merchants and commoners. The universality of Urdu, with its ability to incorporate and adapt words from other languages, ensured its survival and growth. Even today, Hindi speakers unknowingly use an estimated 300 Urdu-origin words daily, reflecting the deep imprint of Urdu on the subcontinent's linguistic landscape.

However, the advent of colonial rule disrupted this continuity. British policies systematically undermined Urdu's dominance, setting the stage for its decline. Despite these challenges, the language endured through its integration into Indian cinema, which became a major cultural force in the mid-20th century.

Part 2: Colonial and Post-Colonial Factors

5 Colonial Factors (British Empire)

The arrival of the British East India Company in the 18th century marked a shift in the subcontinent's linguistic and cultural priorities. The British introduced English as the language of administration, replacing Persian, and by extension marginalizing Urdu.

This policy shift was part of a broader strategy to consolidate power by dismantling indigenous systems of governance and culture.

The “divide and rule” strategy employed by the British deepened linguistic and cultural divides. Hindi, written in the Devanagari script, was promoted as a counterbalance to Urdu, which was increasingly associated with Muslim identity. This deliberate linguistic polarization sowed communal discord, further marginalizing Urdu in public institutions. British policies not only undermined Urdu’s administrative utility but also eroded its cultural significance, relegating it to a symbolic role in Muslim communities.

6 Post-Colonial Factors (Division of India and Pakistan)

The Partition of 1947 dealt a severe blow to Urdu. While it became the national language of Pakistan, in India, it faced an uncertain future. The association of Urdu with Pakistan and Muslim identity fueled its marginalization in post-independence India. Hindi was elevated as the official language, and government resources were directed toward its promotion. Urdu, once the language of administration and culture, was sidelined in favor of a nationalist agenda that prioritized Hindi as a unifying force.

The communal tensions that accompanied Partition further isolated Urdu. Its rich literary heritage and historical significance were overshadowed by political narratives that portrayed it as foreign or divisive. Despite this, Urdu retained a cultural foothold through poetry, music, and cinema, which continued to celebrate its beauty and versatility.

7 Urdu in India from 1940 to 1970

During the mid-20th century, Urdu found a lifeline in Indian cinema, which embraced the language for its poetic and lyrical qualities. Ghazal Gohs like Josh Malihabadi, Firaq Gorakhpuri, Akbar Allahabadi, Jigar Moradabadi, Shahryar, Mohsin Naqvi, Faiz Ahmed Faiz, Noon Meem Rashid, Bashir Badr, Shaayar Lakhnawi, Kaifi Aazmi, Majaz Lakhnawi, Shakeel Badayuni, Qateel Shifai, Bekal Utsahi, Sudarshan Fakir, Dilawar Figaar, Ahmed Faraz, Nida Fazli, Munir Niazi, Nasir Kazmi and Sahir Ludhianvi. Especially amongst the Bollywood lyricist Sahir Ludhianvi and Kaifi Azmi produced timeless songs that kept Urdu alive in public consciousness.

Educational institutions and mushairas (poetry gatherings) also played a role in sustaining the language. However, the dominance of Hindi in education and media, coupled with changing political and cultural priorities, began to erode Urdu’s influence by the late 1960s. The language’s gradual exclusion from public and institutional spaces marked the beginning of its decline, setting the stage for the challenges it faces today.

Part 3: Decline and Sociopolitical Challenges

8 Decline Begins (1970 Onwards)

The decline of Urdu began in earnest in the 1970s, driven by a confluence of sociopolitical, economic, and cultural changes. The rise of Hindi as the dominant language in Indian public and institutional life played a significant role in sidelining Urdu. Educational policies increasingly favored Hindi and regional languages, leaving Urdu marginalized in curricula and public discourse. Moreover, the rise of television and the decline of radio, which had been a bastion for Urdu's literary and cultural presence, marked a pivotal shift. As cinema adapted to changing audience tastes, the intricate lyricism of Urdu poetry gave way to simpler, more accessible lyrics that prioritized Hindi norms.

Cultural shifts further contributed to Urdu's decline. The post-70s generation, influenced by globalization and Western culture, gravitated towards English as a language of aspiration and opportunity. Urdu, increasingly associated with older generations and a specific religious identity, struggled to maintain relevance. The declining presence of Urdu newspapers, magazines, and educational institutions reflected the diminishing interest in the language, especially in urban centers.

9 Changing Times: Media and the Loss of Poetry

The transformation of Indian media in the late 20th century had a profound impact on Urdu. Television and cinema, once vital platforms for Urdu, increasingly catered to audiences demanding visual spectacle and simpler storytelling. The lyrical depth of Urdu poetry, which had long been central to Bollywood songs, became less valued as the industry prioritized commercial success over artistic integrity. Iconic lyricists like Sahir Ludhianvi and Majrooh Sultanpuri gave way to a new wave of songwriters who embraced colloquialism and avoided Urdu's complex linguistic beauty.

The advent of satellite television in the 1990s further marginalized Urdu. Western music genres like pop, rap, and RB gained prominence, leaving little room for the traditional ghazals and qawwalis that had kept Urdu alive. Platforms like All India Radio, once champions of Urdu culture, saw their influence wane. Urdu, which once resonated across diverse audiences, found itself confined to niche platforms like mushairas (poetry recitals) and specialized literary events.

10 Psychological and Social Perspectives

Urdu's decline is also rooted in shifting psychological and social attitudes. Research highlights the unique cognitive impact of Urdu poetry, which activates autobiographical memory and fosters emotional resonance. However, modern trends have moved away from such collective, universal experiences toward individualistic, trend-driven content. The younger generation's preference for instant gratification and transient entertainment has diminished the appeal of Urdu's reflective, layered artistry.

Socioeconomic factors also play a role. As education and employment increasingly prioritize English and Hindi, Urdu's practical utility has eroded. Families who once passed down Urdu as a cultural legacy now prioritize languages deemed more valuable in the job market. This shift reflects broader societal changes that equate linguistic proficiency with economic mobility, relegating Urdu to the periphery.

11 Political Agenda to Divide India and Eliminate Urdu

Urdu's marginalization is inseparable from the political agendas that have shaped modern India. The British colonial "divide and rule" policy created a linguistic schism, branding Urdu as a language of Muslims and Hindi as a symbol of Hindu nationalism. Post-independence, these divisions deepened as nationalist policies prioritized Hindi, systematically excluding Urdu from education and governance.

The rise of pseudo-nationalism further exacerbated this divide. Urdu institutions faced neglect, with government funding directed away from their preservation. The language's association with Partition and Pakistan rendered it a target for nationalist narratives that framed it as unpatriotic or foreign. These policies and perceptions effectively erased Urdu from the public sphere, limiting its reach and influence.

Part 4: Survival and the Path Forward

12 The Four E's and the Public's Role

Urdu's decline cannot be fully understood without examining the public's shifting engagement with cultural content, categorized into the "Four E's": Educational, Emotional, Empowering, and Entertaining content.

Educational Content - Historically, Urdu thrived as an educational tool, serving as the medium of instruction and intellectual discourse in schools and universities. Poetry and prose formed the backbone of a rich literary curriculum. However, the prioritization of English and Hindi in modern education systems relegated Urdu to an optional subject, limiting its exposure to younger generations. Without institutional support, Urdu's presence in educational content diminished, weakening its role in shaping cultural identity.

Emotional content, such as poetry and songs, once resonated deeply with audiences. Urdu's intrinsic ability to evoke universal emotions made it a cornerstone of Indian cinema and literature. For example, ghazals and nazms written by luminaries like Mir and Ghalib fostered a collective cultural memory. Yet, as society became more individualistic, entertainment trends shifted toward genres like pop and rap, where the emotional connection is more self-centered and less communal. This trend has marginalized Urdu's reflective artistry in favor of transient, trend-driven content.

Empowering content, which inspires ambition and self-improvement, also played a role.

Urdu, once seen as a pathway to prestige and success, lost this status as English became synonymous with global opportunity. In modern India, economic mobility often hinges on English proficiency, pushing Urdu further into obscurity.

Entertaining content, which appeals to short attention spans, shifted the cultural zeitgeist. Platforms like TikTok and Instagram emphasize brevity, leaving little room for Urdu's layered, nuanced expression. The public's evolving preferences thus play a critical role in dictating Urdu's decline.

13 Today's Urdu: Surviving in Niches

Despite its challenges, Urdu continues to survive, albeit in niches. Platforms like Rekhta and Applause Adab have emerged as vital spaces for Urdu enthusiasts. Rekhta, in particular, has revolutionized the accessibility of Urdu poetry and literature, offering vast digital archives and hosting popular festivals that attract diverse audiences. Similarly, mushairas (poetry recitals), once a staple of social life, have transitioned to online spaces, reaching global audiences through YouTube and social media.

Pakistani television serials have also kept Urdu alive, especially among South Asian diaspora communities. Iconic dramas like *Humsafar* and *Zindagi Gulzar Hai* showcase the language's beauty, blending traditional themes with contemporary storytelling. Instagram poets like Rupi Kaur, while writing in English, draw inspiration from Urdu's metaphorical richness, indirectly keeping its spirit alive. Moreover, Urdu thrives in diaspora communities where cultural preservation takes precedence. Cities like Toronto, London, and New York host Urdu literary events, ensuring the language remains vibrant outside its native lands.

However, this survival comes with limitations. Urdu's presence in niche spaces risks isolating it from the broader public. Without integration into mainstream platforms, Urdu's audience may remain limited to enthusiasts, curbing its potential for revival on a larger scale.

14 The Path Forward

Reviving Urdu requires concerted efforts across multiple domains. Education must play a central role, with schools integrating Urdu into curricula as a language of heritage rather than a religious or political marker. Government initiatives to fund Urdu institutions, publications, and libraries could provide much-needed support. Media platforms must also champion Urdu, incorporating it into modern formats like podcasts, music videos, and web series that appeal to younger audiences.

Public involvement is equally crucial. Cultural festivals, Open-Mics, workshops, and online courses can engage audiences and promote Urdu as a living, evolving language. Collaboration between India and Pakistan on shared linguistic heritage could further strengthen Urdu's global presence. Ultimately, the responsibility lies not only with institutions but also with individuals who value Urdu's legacy. By embracing both traditional

and modern mediums, Urdu can reclaim its status as a unifying force that transcends borders and generations.

Conclusion

The decline of Urdu is a complex narrative interwoven with political, cultural, and social shifts. Yet, despite these challenges, the language's rich legacy endures in niche spaces, cherished by a devoted community. As we move forward, it is crucial to remember that Urdu's survival depends not only on institutional support but also on the passion and dedication of individuals who continue to celebrate its beauty.

To conclude, I leave you with these words by the renowned poet Javed Akhtar:

اُردُو کو ہم اِک روز مِٹا دیں گے جہاں سے
یہ بات بھی کِسبخت نے اُردُو میں کہی ہے۔
- جاوید اختر

And a personal quote of mine:

"Once you fall in love with Urdu, everything and everyone will fall in love with you."

- Zafar